

STRUCTURE OF CAR SPRINGS AND THEIR TECHNICAL SERVICE

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Annotation: The road consists of unevenness, the impulses of which are transmitted to the body and have a negative effect on the cargo or passenger. To reduce this effect, it is necessary to insert an elastic part (spring, spring, pneumatic balloon, etc.) between the body and the wheel.

To transmit the thrust force from the driving wheels to the driven ones and to dissipate the kinetic energy of the car with the help of the braking force on the braked wheels, the steering arms are necessary to receive the forces connecting the wheel to the body. It is also necessary to dampen the vibrations caused by the impulses caused by road irregularities.

The suspensions accept traction and braking forces, impulses generated by road irregularities, reduce them to the standard level, and reduce the amplitude and duration of vibrations[1,2].

Figure 1. The main scheme of the suspension: 1- spring front bracket, 2- frame, 3- spring, 4- cover, 5- buffer, 6- buffer cover, 7- shock absorber, 8- shock absorber bracket, 9- rear bracket of spring, 10- rubber pad, 11- bracket cover, 12- damper finger, 13- rubber bushing, 14- gasket, 15- fastening bolt, 16-ladder, 17- gaskets.

During the operation of the suspension, the pushing force of the torque transmitted from the transmission to the leading wheel pushes the body (frame) forward through the guiding part, the elastic part softens the impulses transmitted from road irregularities, and the damping part moves the body (frame) in the vertical direction due to the elastic part. dampens the vibration[3].

We know that according to the types of elastic elements, suspensions are divided into metal - spring, spring, torsion and non-metallic - pneumatic, hydropneumatic suspensions.

Leaf springs are used as an elastic device in spring suspensions. Depending on the number of lists, resources are single-list, double-list and multi-list (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Types of resources according to the number of lists.

The spring is made up of individually curved sheets assembled together. Steel sheets have a right angle section, the same width and different lengths. The curvature of the sheets is not the same, but depends on their length. As the sheets shorten in length, their curvature increases, which ensures that they fit tightly together when folded. Varying curvature also ensures that the longest sheet (core sheet) is unloaded.

To keep the sheets in the folded position, they are tensioned by a centering bolt. The head of the centering bolt serves as a mounting pin when assembling the spring to the bridge beam[4,5].

Clamps (clamps) are used to ensure that the sheets do not spread in both directions and to transfer force to the sheets located below the core sheet on the way back (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: View of the spring and its clamps.

When the spring is deformed, its length changes. If the spring, in addition to the function of an elastic part, also performs the function of a guiding device, one end of the spring should be recorded relative to the frame, and the configuration of the other end should allow its length to change freely. The front end is fastened with a finger, and the rear end is often connected with a sliding hook.

If a device other than a spring performs the function of a guiding device, usually both ends of the spring should move freely in the longitudinal direction.

If the ability to simultaneously perform the functions of elastic, guiding and damping devices is considered an advantage of leaf springs, its disadvantage is its high mass and low resistance to wear compared to other types of elastic devices.

Disturbances in resources: The main reason for the breakage of the springs is loading with more than the standard load and the formation of fatigue cracks over time, that is, if the springs have been used for more than ten years. When a truck is driven on a bumpy road with a heavier load than allowed, one of the springs may snap on the next impact. Old springs have micro-cracks, bends and other defects that cause them to break under load. If the spring is installed incorrectly, it can also break when attached to the frame.

It is not necessary to weld the spring. The springs bend under load, and the welding area is not designed to bend[6,7].

Car maintenance: During the maintenance of cars, the correct installation of the front and rear axles of the car, the mounting angles of the front wheels are checked and, if necessary, adjusted, the fingers of the front and rear springs are checked on the 2-TS. The spring, the fastening of the spring-loaded parts to the frame is checked. Also, during the inspection of the resources, their broken or torn lists (sheets) are identified. Springs should not have any noticeable longitudinal displacement. Such a situation can occur due to the cutting of the central bolt. When checking the reliable fastening of the springs, special attention should be paid to how the extension nuts are tightened and to the absence of wear in the bushings that fix the spring hingedly. If one end of the spring is attached to rubber pads, check the integrity of the pads and their correct location on the support. The nuts on the extension rods and clamps of the spring are tightened evenly, first the front ones (according to the movement of the car), then the next ones.

The elasticity of the springs is checked by their arc shape in the free state. This indicator can be determined by pulling a string between the ends of the spring and measuring the vertical distance from the string to the center of the bent core sheet. The arc of springs in car suspensions should not differ more than 10 mm from each other. If the springs make noises when the car moves, as well as rust on the plates, they should be cleaned of dirt, washed in kerosene and lubricated with graphite.

Conclusions: In order to prevent rapid failure of springs, i.e., breakage, it is necessary to use them correctly during operation. In this:

- Preventing the springs from being loaded with more than the standard load;
- Timely and correct execution of technical maintenance work extends the service life (resource) of resources;

- Also, when moving with a load, as a result of sudden braking, breakage due to inertial forces is also observed

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